

Adjustment Problems Among the Aged Teachers in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Adjustment problems among the aged Secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Four research questions guided the study and the study employed the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised all the retired secondary school teachers in Anambra State. A sample of 330 retired secondary school teachers was used. The self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Data collected for research questions were analyzed using item mean with benchmark of 2.5 for acceptance. The results showed that Loss of memory, Health challenges, Loss of role functions, Loss of friends, Loss of recognition, Limited personal income, not able to take care of financial needs and being dependent on family members for basic need among others are some of the adjustment problems among the aged secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended among others that the aged should be encouraged by providing support networks to the elderly for instance, ensuring that they get their pension and gratuity, providing their physical needs such as feeding, finance, good living arrangements, among others

Key words: Adjustment Problems, Aged, Teachers, Mental, Physiological

Introduction

Aging population has recently become an issue attracting guidance and counselling attention in both developed and developing countries of the world. This is as a result of the dramatic increase in the number of the aged within the population (United Nations, 2005). Globally, the number of people aged within 60 years and above was approximately 280 million in 2005, accounting for 7% of the global population (U.S. Bureau of Census, 2008). World Health

Organization (2005) projected that by 2050, the over 60 years population will increase by 60%. In America, the aggregate of the elderly is the most rapidly expanding segment of the population, and in 2004, these elderly citizens accounted for 11.3% and by 2050 21% of the population is projected to be of this age group (US Senate on Special Committee on Aging, 2008).

The global phenomenon of aging population affects Nigeria too. As per UN classification, the African society would progress from a 'mature society to an aging society'. The demographic transition has been accompanied by a social and cultural transition that gives rise to many adjustment problems for the elderly. The social forces such as modernization and urbanization have not only disrupted the traditional social life of the elderly, but also led to the desertion of the elderly by their children migrating to urban areas. The effects of children leaving home could be one of the emotionally threatening forces by the aged. Losing the spouse is yet another disruptive event in the life of an elderly person. Widowhood, in general, results in social isolation and loneliness (Bowling & Cartwright, 1993); guilt and anger (Glick, 1994) and increased probability of emotional illness (Ferraro, 1995). Adjustment problems in widowhood should also be seen in the light of shift in the family structure.

Aging is a natural phenomenon that alludes to changes, which happen during the life span and result in contrasts in structure and function between the adolescent and the elderly (Fedarko, 2011). Traditionally, the term, aged, has been referred to people who have attained certain age chronologically. Aging is an unavoidable process in which physiological, emotional and mental changes are seen in declining form. It is, otherwise, called closing period of life expectancy. It is a life spanning process of growth and development running from birth to death. It is generally associated with decline in the functional capacity of the organs of the body due to physiological transformation (Fedarko, 2011). According to Aeri and Sharma (2001), old age means physical liability, declining mental ability, the gradual giving up of role in social activities and a shift in economic status and moving from monetary independence to monetary reliance on others for support.

With advancing age, all of the body systems eventually demonstrate reduced efficiency, slowed building and replacing and actual loss of tissue. Aging is inevitably accompanied by physical decline, muscles atrophy, brittleness of bones, weakening of vision, hearing loss. Many elderly people also suffer loss of mental and emotional capacity resulting in depression, apathy, dementia, reduced logical reasoning among others. As a result of aging, the elderly people disengage themselves from social contacts and interactions. They engage less frequently in social roles and social activities, resulting in their invertible withdrawal from their environment and society in general. In response to this decline in social, emotional and mental ability, most individualized nations have adopted social benefits programmed for the elderly and have created legal institutions and laws to confront the legal problems associated with the mental, emotional and social consequences of aging (Edeh, 2014). In traditional African culture, elderly people were normally happily associated with and cared for by the family unit. The family has been the most natural and conducive social association for the care and support of the elderly people in Africa. However, the traditional family support system of older people is experiencing a change hence; Sijuwade (2008) shows that adjustment of the aged has been treated as a gender-based issue.

Maslow in Neha, Harish, Deepika (2014) look at adjustment as a process of planned satisfaction of hierarchy of needs from warm and caring relationship to others. According to Dashiell in Neha, Harish, Deepika (2014), adjustment is a process that covers the individual's life span operating within a complex environment or field. The process is goal directed behaviour instituted by a need which may rise at any level within the hierarchy of needs ranging from elementary psychological issue through the most complicated psychological symbolization. Kulshrestha (1979) opines that adjustment process is a manner by which an individual endeavours to deal with stress, anxiety, tensions and conflicts to meets his or her needs. In this process, the individual either makes efforts to maintain a harmonious relationship with environment or changes his behaviour to fit their need. The adjustment of the aging person depends upon the degree to which his personal and environmental circumstances offer opportunities or pose as threats to the satisfaction of his needs. The inability to adjust can bring about bitterness, withdrawal, depression and anxiety (Chokkanatham & Lee, 2005; Sharma, 2008). The burdens and vulnerabilities remarkable to the aging process which include chronic physical problems, cognitive impairment and substantial emotional losses may further contribute to anxiety (Porzych, Kedziora, Porzych, Polak & Motyl, 2005; Ingle & Nath, 2008).

The importance of the well-being of the elderly is profoundly stressed in the available literature. In a study, Lazarus (1989) observes a significant difference between spouse living and spouse not living groups (meaning what) of elderly in emotional and general adjustments. Marital satisfaction is found to be the best predictor of mental health and global happiness for both men and women. Wearne (2007), in his research on the prevalence of psychosocial challenges among the elderly people in the rural communities of Imo State, observes that it is on the increase especially in the developing countries. He estimates in his study that the prevalence is 78% and that it will increase by four-folds by 2030. Interaction with some of the elderly persons revealed feeling of rejection by their immediate relations and the community. Ajomale (2006) observes that the traditional bonds between the elderly and their young family members are gradually becoming weak. In fact is at the verge of collapsing. With a collapsing extended family, these elderly persons no longer enjoy the care and support of the family members and relatives as is the case in traditional African society, thereby exposing them to adjustment challenges of various dimensions.

Several studies also reported that a large number of old men and women badly need health care, financial assistance, social recognition and counselling services to cope up with stress for overcoming 'death anxiety', 'sense of isolation', feeling of social deprivation due to negligence, "feeling of disability and dependency", "low social esteem and lethargic feelings"(Ajomale, 2006) . In Nigeria, precisely in Anambra State, the elderly suffer a lot of hardship in our contemporary society. They constitute the least fortunate group in the society, as there is visible evidence of hardship and begging among in them, especially in rural communities, where the majority of them live (Ayisonbola, 2004). A cursory look at the implementation of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by the Federal Government of Nigeria shows that there was little or no consideration for this vulnerable population group. This poses a big problem.

More so, as a result of modernization, there was a change in family structure in Nigeria which led to disintegration of the concept of extended family system. The traditional function of the family like care and social assistance of the older members of the family was gradually crumbling. Growing old mechanisms means deterioration of physical, mental, emotional and social being that are necessary for effective performance in society. Old age in our society presents an individual with varieties of potential adjustment challenges and stress, most of which are in the categories of mental, emotional, social and personal losses. They experienced a loss of social roles, loss of self-esteem, limited economic resources and depleted social and psychological network. Hence, the need to find out the adjustment problems among the aged secondary school teachers in Anambra State.

The general purpose of the study is to examine the adjustment problems among the aged in Anambra State. However, the specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify the mental adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone.
2. Identify the emotional adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone.
3. Determine the social adjustment problems faced by the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone.
4. Identify the financial adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the mental adjustment problems among the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone?
2. What are the emotional adjustment problems among the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone?
3. What are the social adjustment problems among the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone?
4. What are the financial adjustment problems among the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone?

METHOD

The study employed descriptive survey design. Nworgu (2006) opines that descriptive surveys are concerned with those studies which aim at collecting data and explaining in a systematic manner, the characteristic features of a given population. The choice of this design is based on the fact that it would enable the researchers to collect and analyze data as they are without any manipulation.

The target population for the study includes all the aged secondary school teachers from 65 years old and above, both males and females, in Anambra State with total retired teacher population (2016-2019) of four thousand three hundred and seventy (Post Primary Schools

Service Commission). The sample consists 330 retired Secondary school teachers within Awka Education Zone, Anambra State obtained through purposive sampling Technique. Through purposive sampling technique, sixty six (66) retired teachers were selected from each of the five Local government areas in Awka Education Zone making it a total of three hundred and thirty aged teachers.

The instrument for data collection of this study is a questionnaire developed by the researchers. The questionnaire is titled “Adjustment Problems among the Aged Teachers” (APAT). The questionnaire is made up of eighteen structured items that are based on research questions of the study. The instrument has four sections of A, B, C and D; section A contains mental adjustment problems, Section B contains emotional adjustment problems, section C contains social adjustment problems and Section D contains financial adjustment problems of the aged. The items were measured using a 4-point Scale of always, 4points, sometimes, 3 points, 2 rarely and never, I point. The respondents were asked to choose from the options their experiences fall in this recent time. The content validity of the instrument was carried out. To ascertain this, the researchers presented three copies of the questionnaire to two experts in Guidance and Counselling and one to an expert in Measurement and Evaluation, all in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The experts were also presented with copies of the research objectives and research questions as a guide. They were requested to assess the suitability of the language, the comprehensiveness, adequacy and relevance of the items in addressing the research questions, bearing in mind the purpose of the study. Their comments, suggestions and correction were accommodated and used to modify the instrument. The trial test of the instrument was carried out using test-retest reliability techniques. Ten (20) retired teachers were randomly selected from Onitsha education zone, with comparable characteristics, and the test items were administered to the group. After an interval of two weeks, the same test was administered to the same group who responded to the test previously. The reliability co-efficient was determined using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients, which also determined the suitability of the instrument for the study, and it yielded a coefficient value of 0.83. Data collected was collated, tallied and analyzed by descriptive statistics using means scores and presented in tables. A 4 point scale was used. The mid-point of 2.50 criterion mean is accepted as positive response.

Results

Table 1: Responses showing the mental adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers. The number of responses =330

S/N	ITEMS	X	Decision
1	Loss of memory	2.51	Agree
2	Depression	2.10	Disagree
3	Abandonment	2.57	Agree
4	Not able to do much things again	3.67	Agree
5	Health challenges	3.52	Agree
	GRAND MEAN	2.87	

Table 1 show that 139 of the respondents always experience loss of memory, whereas only 68 do not. A mean response score of 2.51 shows that many of the respondents experience loss of memory. The table also shows that many of the respondents do experience abandonment; health challenges and inability to do many things. Considering the grand mean which above 2.5, it could be said that the respondents agreed that the above items are the mental adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone.

Table II: Responses showing emotional adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers. The number of responses =330

S/N	ITEMS	X	Dec
6	Loneliness	2.56	Agree
7	Isolation	2.85	Agree
8	Loss of self-esteem	2.64	Agree
9	Loss of role functions	3.25	Agree
10	Loss of skills	3.43	Agree
	GRAND MEAN	2.95	

Table 2 shows that a mean response of 2.56 of the respondents experience loneliness. A mean response score of 2.64 shows that many of the respondents experience loss of self-esteem. More than half of 184 of the respondents felt lonely and isolated, only a few 67 did not. In the area of role functions 165 of the respondents were bothered much on loss of role function, while only a few were not. A mean response score of 3.43 also shows that many of the respondents experience loss of skills. Considering the grand mean which above 2.5, it could be said that the respondents agreed that the above items are the emotional adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers in Awka Education Zone.

Table III: Responses showing how social adjustment problems faced by the aged secondary school teachers. The number of responses =330

S/N	ITEMS	X	Dec
11	Loss of friends	1.57	Disagree
12	Loss of recognition	1.68	Disagree
13	Loss of interest in sexuality	2.75	Agree
14	Loss of interest in social gathering	2.42	Agree
	GRAND MEAN	2.10	

The table III above shows that in items 11 and 12, the respondents were not challenged by the problems of loss of friends and loss of recognition since the mean scores were below the decision rule of 2.5. However, in items 13 and 14, the respondents agree that Loss of interest in sexuality and Loss of interest in social gathering are some of the social adjustments problems they face.

Table IV: Responses financial adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers. The number of responses =330

S/N	ITEMS	X	Dec
15	Limited personal income	3.78	Agree
16	Not able to take care of your financial needs	2.56	Agree
17	Being dependent on family members for your basic needs	2.54	Agree
18	Not satisfied with the present income	2.92	Agree
	GRAND MEAN	2.95	

The table IV above shows that the respondents agreed to items 15, 16, 17 and 18 with the mean scores of 3.78, 2.56, 2.54 and 2.92 respectively. Therefore, considering the grand mean score which is 2.95, we can conclude that the respondents agreed that the above items are the financial adjustments problems among the aged teachers in Awka Education Zone.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from research question one showed that more than half of the respondents studied experience Loss of memory, Depression, Abandonment, inability to do many things and Health challenges. The study agrees with Borson (2005) who identifies in his study on prevalence of dementia in older adult that decline mental skills are inevitable part of later life. However, this finding disagreed with the result of the study carried out by Wragg in Edeh (2014) who identifies in a longitudinal study that cognitive function does not decline in a substantial portion of the elderly. The findings also revealed that the aged experience abandonment and health problems. The study is in line with Bose (1990) who points out that the old people had feeling of being abandoned by the society because nobody had the time to sit with them. The aged had feeling of being neglected by society and the members of the family as their children did not allow them to mix up with others.

The findings from research question two revealed that majority of the respondents are faced with challenges of loneliness and isolation. This finding is in line with the study carried out by Age Well Research and Advocacy Centre U.S.A (2010). The Center carried out a nationwide survey in January 2010 to study, identify and understand the challenges of isolation in old age. The study identified that the majority of the elderly who lived in rural areas reportedly felt isolated and lonely. It was also revealed in the same study that majority of the elderly who lived in rural areas were socially and emotionally isolated. This study was equally in support of the study done by Touhy and Jett (2014) on social isolation among the elderly population. He identified that many elderly people experienced social isolation and loneliness which increase with age. However, this result was not in agreement with Russel (2004) who identified in his study on isolation and loneliness in old age that 62% of his sample reported that loneliness and isolation were not a problem to them.

The findings from research question four also revealed that the respondents experience loss of role functions, loss of self-esteem and self-worth. This finding agrees with the findings of Fry (2004). In his study on form of losses the elderly experienced, he identifies that the single most important and often devastating challenges facing the elderly is the strong sense of loss of identity, self-esteem, and self-worth as well as loss of valued social roles. This finding is in support of Parker (2004), who in a comprehensive survey of emotional challenges of the rural dwelling elderly revealed that multiple/repetitive losses possess a serious emotional challenge to the elderly persons. He stated in study that inadequate coping with the corresponding losses makes the elderly believed that life generally hold no meaning.

This result disagreed with studies done in some parts of Nigeria as reported by Moore (2009) and Blazer (2005). Their studies reveal that most of the elderly can cope adequately with these challenges. Additionally, about a 60% of the sample confirmed that they take these losses as part of life events and so they can adapt and cope with the losses of the past lives. This study also reveals that more than half of the respondents studied cope with the losses they experienced in life.

The findings of the study revealed that most of the respondents experience loss of interest in social gathering and loss of interest in sexuality. The study is in line with Boss (1990) who points out that the aged had feeling of being neglected by the society and the members of the family as their children did not allow them to mix up with others. In old age, they feel they had become less active and due to their poor economic conditions, they cannot attend the social gatherings. Sarah (1980) states that during the retirement period, the aged pass into a new social position with unique roles, expectation and responsibilities. This shift brings about an abrupt reduction in number of roles played and the decline in status and standard of living.

The findings of the study also revealed that the respondents do not experience Loss of friends and Loss of recognition. This finding is in congruence with the findings of Okunola (2010) who identifies in his study on family care and support for the elderly, that there are always contact relationships between the elderly people and their family members and other relatives and the aged are always recognized in the family. This could be as a result of the fact that in the African society, the family that has been the major resource for the elderly and had traditionally been charged with the responsibilities of seeing to the welfare of their elderly relatives no longer cope with the responsibilities due to influence by foreign culture.

The study agrees generally with the view expressed by Hamilton (2006), who reveals that old people in Nigeria generally live and receive care and support at their homes or at the residence of their children or homes of their relatives unlike in developed countries like USA where they receive care mostly at the nursing homes or private day care for the aged. According to him, when children take the responsibilities of caring for their elderly family members, they tend to know them better and love them more dearly.

The study in table four reveals that the respondents experience limited personal income, not inability to care of your financial needs, being dependent on family members for your basic needs and not satisfied with their present income. This study agrees with Asiya in Ezeh (2014)

who posits in his study that the aged are faced with the feelings of apprehension and doubt about the fulfillment of their needs and wants.

Conclusion

This study had been able to examine the adjustment problems among the aged teachers in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the following conclusions were made:

1. Mental adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers in Anambra state: Loss of memory, Abandonment, not able to do many things again and Health challenges.
2. Loneliness, Isolation, Loss of self-esteem, Loss of role functions and Loss of skills are the emotional adjustment problems of the aged secondary school teachers in Anambra state.
3. Loss of friends and Loss of recognition are social adjustment problems among the secondary school teachers while greater number of the respondents agree that Loss of interest in sexuality and Loss of interest in social gathering are social adjustment problems among the secondary school teachers.
4. Limited personal income, not able to take care of your financial needs, being dependent on family members for your basic needs and not satisfied with the present income are the financial adjustment problems among the secondary school teachers.

Implications of the Study

The findings from this study have shown that adjustment problems are prevalent in the state of study. This should not be overlooked due to its serious consequences which eventually lead to untimely death or serious health implications among this vulnerable group of the population.

However, in order to avert this problem, counsellors especially family counsellors should educate the elderly in the rural areas on these problems to ensure their psychosocial wellbeing and graceful aging and, help them to form support groups so as to share their experiences and problems. Civic and recreational centers should be provided for them and they should be encouraged to participate in group living activities which will help them cope with their adjustment problems. The caregivers should also be educated on these problems and how best to care for the elderly and their problems.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and implications of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Increasing the awareness of the public on the needs of the elderly with emphasis on the traditional roles of and responsibilities of the family in the care of the elderly.
2. Civic/recreational centers should be provided for the elderly to help them to gather together to discuss their adjustment challenges and other issues affecting them and by so doing, they are able to cope with the adjustment problems of aging process.
3. Qualitative and Quantitative intergenerational research should be carried out on psychosocial challenges of the elderly in both rural and urban areas so as to identify most

appropriate and effective policy approaches to addressing the issues relating to the elderly.

4. Encouraging community based support networks to the elderly, for instance, ensuring that they get their pension and gratuity, provision of physical needs such as feeding, finance, good living arrangements among others.
5. Workshops, seminars and symposia should be organized in the rural areas on adjustment challenges of the elderly so as to educate families, care givers, counsellors and the community on how best to take care of the elderly and their challenges.

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